

COMPETENCE, COMMITMENT AND WORK MOTIVATION THROUGH QUALITY SERVICE TO THE PERFORMANCE OF EMPLOYEES OF PT. AMERICAN SPRINGBED

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of competence, motivation and commitment through service quality on employee performance. This type of research is survey research with a quantitative approach with an inferential research type. The population and sample used a full sampling technique, namely by assigning as many as 175 respondents. Quantitative research approach with primary and secondary data sources. Data collection using direct observation instruments and questionnaire dissemination. The technical data analysis used in this study uses Partial Least Square (PLS) with SmartPLS Software. The results of the study found that service quality is influenced by work competence and motivation so service quality improvement can be made by increasing employee competence and employee work motivation. Employee performance is influenced by competence, organizational commitment, and service quality, so employee performance improvement can be achieved through increasing competence, commitment, work motivation, and service quality.

Keywords: Competence, Commitment, Work Motivation, Service Quality and Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of a comparatively oriented and competitive company aims to improve employee performance in realizing company goals (Astri, 2022). PT. American Springbed, as one of the manufacturing companies in the Makassar Industrial Estate (KIMA), strives to continue to improve the performance achievements of its employees and service quality by improving competence, commitment, and work motivation directly or indirectly.

To realize employee performance achievements, the company always pays attention to the quality of work services by considering the company's existence in providing services (Endang et al., 2022). Parasuraman (2019) manifests the quality of work services in the form of physical evidence, empathy, reliability, responsiveness and assurance. This is in accordance with its actualization based on strengthening the competence, commitment and motivation of employees. Judging from the physical evidence of the form of services shown, the company has provided various work facilities and work equipment in the form of employees, company buildings, factories, workplaces, material warehouses and fleets that distribute goods from factories to destinations (Fatima, 2022).

The company also shows the form of service in every work activity; the management empathizes with employees to always carry out work with full attention, togetherness, solidarity, and cooperation between leaders and employees, employees and their colleagues, and even with other parties (Herry, 2019). The company also emphasizes the importance of providing quality services by considering reliability in working in accordance with the main duties and functions of each employee (Khalid et al., 2022). Employees are also required to provide responsive service quality by showing a professional ability to handle their field of work, always responding, and being responsible for advancing professional work dynamics in the manufacturing world

(Nelson, 2017). Employees are also required to be able to show job security in every job completion and avoid work risks (Yusni, 2022). All forms of service quality are intended to improve employee performance.

One indication that supports service quality is the improvement of employee performance, which has been oriented toward leadership assessment, not yet oriented to the performance of achieving work results in quantity, quality, efficiency, effectiveness, and work loyalty (Abdul et al., 2022). This needs to be actualized by every business venture in developing work performance (Raffy, 2022).

It can be seen in reality that employees are still unable to develop their performance achievements in quantity, as seen from the large amount of work produced (Chusway, 2021). Carry out work in quantity according to the quality of the work done. Not considering the efficiency of fast and precise working time, it is still often found that the use of budget effectiveness is not appropriate in its allocation (Dekker, 2017). As a result, performance achievement has less influence on realizing service quality (Alamsyah et al., 2019).

Service quality and employee performance of PT. American Springbed is still not as expected. The results show that competence, commitment and work motivation that are understood and actualized by employees have not contributed to improving the quality of service and employee performance. It can be seen that there are still employees who are not competent in their field of work in terms of knowledge, skills, experience, and mastery attitude. Such as not knowing what to do, not being skilled in completing tasks according to their expertise, being less experienced in carrying out work in accordance with initiative, and not having an attitude of mastering the field of work professionally (Researcher Observation, 2023). Competent people always apply quality and ample services to improve their performance (Julie et al., 2022).

In addition, in developing the existence of employees and increasing their work commitment, they always consider the actualization of their work commitment (Astri, 2022). The reality of employees is often questioned about the actualization of pledges in realizing quality services (Chusway, 2021). Questionable commitment to developing rules that are in accordance with applicable norms (Follet, 2017). Employees also often maintain the ability to maintain organizational success, which involves their existence always being committed to improving performance (Fatima, 2022). Often, employees are not empathetic in realizing service quality, sometimes violate organizational rules and attributes, and do not have pride in maintaining organizational achievements (Khalid et al., 2022). Employees who have affective, normative and continuous commitment will realize the achievement of organizational results and goals (Ehsan, 2021). These results are in the form of realizing service quality and performance achievements (Nabizadeh, 2022).

There are still employees who feel unmotivated to realize good achievements, power and work affiliation (Marius, 2020). Employees often actualize their self-development to excel according to the field of work they achieve (Peter & John, 2018). Employees do not have power in accordance with the work authority that must be actualized in themselves and low socialization in self-development to pursue a career together with their colleagues (Sunadji, 2022). This is what causes employees to be less motivated to realize quality services, which contributes to improving company performance (Nabizadeh, 2022). Employees who have good achievement motivation easily realize service quality and improve their performance.

2. METHOD

The subjects of this study were employees of PT. American Springbeg. This type of research is survey research with a quantitative approach with an inferential research type. The population and sample used a *full sampling* technique, namely by assigning as many as 175 respondents. Data sources are primary data and secondary data. The research instrument used is to capture data through questionnaires. The technical method of data analysis used in this study is using *Partial Least Square* (PLS) with *SmartPLS Software*.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Designing Structural Models (*Inner Model*)

Structural Model or *Inner model* that describes a relationship between latent variables based on the concept of *substantive theory*. The design of the structural model is based on the formulation of the problem or hypothesis of this study. The structural relationship between these variables can be expressed in the path equation contained in the conceptual framework of this study as follows:

$$Y1 = f. (X1, X2, X3)$$

$$Z1 = f. \{X1, X2, X3, Y1\}$$

Information: X1 = Competency

X2 = Commitment

X3 = Work Motivation

Y1 = Quality of Service

Z1 = Employee Performance

The Inner Model design in this study can be explained in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Structural Model Design (Inner model)

Sumber: Smart-PLS Model

Designing the Measurement Model (*Outer Model*)

The measurement model or outer model describes the relationship of each indicator block with its latent variables. The design of the measurement model in this study determines the nature of the indicators of each latent variable, whether the design of the measurement model is reflexive or formative, by referring to the operational definition of the variable.

Constructing a Path Diagram

In this study, constructing a path diagram is done by drawing a structural model that connects latent variables and inserting observed variables or indicators into latent variables. The design of the path diagram drawing, along with the measurement model, can be seen in Figure 2:

Figure 2: Design of Path Diagrams and Measurement Models

Source: Smart-PLS Model (processed)

Information:

- X1 : Competence
- X2 : Commitment
- X3 : Work Motivation
- Y1 : Quality of Service
- Z1 : Employee Performance
- : Construction.
- : Indicator.
- : Influence.
- > : Formed

Convert Path Diagram to System of Equations

The path diagram that has been formed is then converted into the measurement model equation (outer model) and processed into the structural model equation (*inner model*).

Parameter Estimation Calculation Method (Estimate)

The calculation parameter estimation method in Smart-PLS is the least square method. The calculation process in this study is carried out by iteration, where the iteration will stop if convergent conditions have been reached. The parameter estimation method in the Smart-PLS application includes 3 (three) things, namely: (1) Weight estimate, which is an estimate used to calculate latent variable data. (2) A path estimate is an estimate used to connect latent variables and load estimates between latent variables and indicators. (3) *Means* and location parameters, i.e., values of regression and interception constants) to relate indicators and latent variables

Uji Kesesuaian Model (Goodness of Fit Model)

The goodness of fit model, often referred to as the conformity test, is carried out on Smart-PLS software by doing the *outer model* and inner model.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing generally uses *explanatory research* methods. Namely, method approaches that use Smart-PLS. This is due to this method of testing the Hypothesis. In this study, hypothesis testing (β , γ , and λ) was carried out using the Bootstrap Resampling method developed by Gaiser & Stone. The Bootstrap Resampling method is a method that allows the application of freely distributed data that does not require the assumption of free distribution and does not require large data bursts (recommended for a minimum sample of 30 respondents). Hypothesis testing can be seen through t-statistical values and probability values. The test in question uses a statistical value and a probability or alpha value of 1%. The hypothesis in this study that has been established can be accepted if $T_{calculate} > T_{tabel}$ and $P_{value} < 0.05$ ($\alpha=5\%$).

Data Analysis

Outer Model Measurement

The data analysis used to prove the hypothesis in this study is a partial least square analysis analysis. The steps of the Partial Least Square method carried out in this study can be explained as follows:

Outer Model Measurement

Measuring the outer model means specifying the correlation between latent variables and indicators carried out with several measurements, namely, Convergent validity of the measurement model with reflexive indicators in this study, including competence, organizational commitment, work motivation, service quality, and employee performance, can be seen from the correlation between indicator scores and construct scores. Each indicator is said to be reliable if it has an *outer loading* value above 0.500.

Figure 3: Correlation Model of Constructs and Indicators

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Discriminant Validity

Ghozali (2018) suggests using AVE as a measure of convergent validity, where an AVE value of at least 0.500 indicates a good measure of convergent validity.

Table 1: Discriminant Validity Test Results

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Criterion
Competence	0,574	Qualify
Organizational Commitment	0,719	Qualify
Work Motivation	0,516	Qualify
Quality of Service	0,508	Qualify
Employee Performance	0,546	Qualify

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that all variables have a high discriminant validity value of above 0.5, so based on the table, a conclusion can be drawn that the reflexive measurement model estimated for the construct of competence, organizational commitment, work motivation, employee satisfaction and performance has met the criteria that the construct has good reliability.

Measuring the Inner Model

The inner model is a structural model used to predict causality relationships (cause-and-effect relationships) between latent variables or variables that cannot be measured directly.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination is basically a range that measures the model's ability to explain changes in the dependent variable. Based on the results of the study, the value of the coefficient of determination (R-square) of the service quality variable was 0.409. The value of the coefficient of determination (R-square) of 0.409 means that the magnitude of the influence of competence, organizational commitment and work motivation on service quality is 40.9%.

Based on the results of the study, the value of the coefficient of determination (R-square) of the employee performance variable was 0.806. The value of the coefficient of determination (R-square) of 0.806 means that the magnitude of the influence of competence, organizational commitment, work motivation and service quality on employee performance variables is 80.6%.

Hypothesis Testing

Furthermore, the relationship test between constructs or hypothesis tests can be assessed by looking at t-statistics from the estimation of structural model indicators from SmartPLS processing. The limit for rejecting and accepting the proposed hypothesis is 1.98 (significance table 5% = 1.98). The results of t-statistical estimation can be seen in the results for Path Coefficients in the following table:

Table 2: Inner model measurement results

Information	Original Sample (O)	t-Statistics (O/STDEV)	p-value	Results
Competency (X1) → Quality of Service (Y)	0,531	3,898	0,000	Influential
Organizational Commitment (X2) → Quality of Service (Y)	-0,215	1,090	0,276	No Effect
Work Motivation (X3) → Quality of Service (Y)	0,403	2,331	0,020	Influential
Competency (X1) → Employee Performance (Z)	0,177	2,094	0,037	Influential
Organizational Commitment (X2) → Employee Performance (Z)	0,636	8,887	0,000	Influential
Work Motivation (X3) → Employee Performance (Z)	0,017	0,219	0,827	No Effect
Quality of Service (Y) → Employee Performance (Z)	0,250	4,138	0,000	Influential

Source: Primary data processed, 2024

Based on table 2, it can be interpreted as follows: (a) The equation model that describes the correlation between latent variables is as follows: Quality of service = 0.531 Competency -0.215 Organizational commitment + 0.403 Work motivation + ϵ , Employee performance = 0.177 Competency + 0.636 Organizational commitment - 0.017 Work motivation + 0.250 Quality of service + ϵ , (b) The results of hypothesis testing on inner model testing at a significance level of 0.05 give a t-statistic value of 3.898 > 1.98 with a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 so that it can be interpreted that competence affects service quality (c) The results of hypothesis testing in inner model testing at a significance level of 0.05 give a t-statistic value of 1.090 < 1.98 with a p-value of 0.276 > 0.05 so that it can be interpreted that organizational commitment has no effect on service quality (d) The results of hypothesis testing on inner model testing at a significance level of 0.05 give a value T-Statistics 2.331 > 1.98 with p-value of

0.020 < 0.05 so that it can be interpreted that work motivation affects service quality. (e) The results of hypothesis testing in inner model testing at a significance level of 0.05 give a t-statistic value of 2.094 > 1.98 with a p-value of 0.037 < 0.05 so that competence can be interpreted as affecting employee performance. (f) The results of hypothesis testing in inner model testing at a significance level of 0.05 give a t-statistic value of 8.887 > 1.98 with a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 so that it can be interpreted that organizational commitment affects employee performance. (g) The results of hypothesis testing in the inner model testing at a significance level of 0.05 give a t-statistic value of 0.219 < 1.98 with a p-value of 0.827 > 0.05 so that it can be interpreted that work motivation does not affect employee performance. (h) The results of hypothesis testing in the inner model testing at a significance level of 0.05 give a t-statistic value of 4.138 > 1.98 with a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 so that it can be interpreted that service quality affects employee performance.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the conclusions of the hypothesis, conclusions can be formulated on research problems, namely 1) competence affects service quality. These results identify that effective and optimal competence can affect the service quality process; 2) organizational commitment has no effect on service quality, these results identify that employee commitment is less likely to depend on service quality; 3) work motivation affects service quality, this result identifies that high work motivation can affect service quality 4) competence affects employee performance, this result identifies that employee competence can have high work quality; 5) organizational commitment affects employee performance, these results identify that organizational commitment can increase employee effectiveness; 6) Work motivation does not affect employee performance. These results identify that the work motivation carried out so far tends not to affect employee performance; 7) Service quality affects employee performance. This result identifies that the quality of service has a positive influence on employee performance.

Recommendations for this study are that continuing to improve employee performance cannot be separated from increasing employee competence and being committed and motivated so that employees realize service quality.

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Reference

- 1) Abdul Imam, Aiman Raza, Faisal Tehseen Shah dan Hasnain Raza, 2022. *Impact of Job Satisfaction on Facet of Organizational Commitment (Affective, Continuance, and Normative Commitment): A Study of Banking Sector Employees of Pakistan*. World Applied Sciences Journal 28 (2): 271-277, 2022 ISSN 1818-4952 © IDOSI Publications, DOI: 10.5829/idosi.wasj.2022.28.02.12468.
- 2) Achim Walter, (2020). *The Impact of Satisfaction, Trust and Relationship Value on Commitment: Theoretical Considerations and Empirical Results for Progress of Organization*. Journal of Management Vol. 19 No. 2, 2020. pp. 194-216.
- 3) Allen, S., and Meyer, G., 2019. *Organization Commitment in Management Perspective*. Published by Prentice Hall, New York.
- 4) Amstrong, Michael and Baron. 2020. *Performance Management*. London Institute of Personnel and Development. Kualitatif dan R&D. Bandung. Alfabeta.

- 5) Ansori, H.A, 2020. Analisis Pengaruh Kompetensi Dan Promosi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Negeri Sipil Pada Sekretariat Daerah Kabupaten Bungo. *Jurnal Ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi* Vol.015, No.01, 50–60.
- 6) Astri Ghina, 2022. *The Influence of Corporate Culture and Organizational Commitment toward Service Quality: Case Study of Civil Government Organization Indonesia*. P-ISSN: 2301-4458 E-ISSN: 2301-8038 Vol. 01, No. 02. Oct 2022.
- 7) Barbara, Berk, (2019). *Organization and Management*. Routledge and Kegan Paul, London.
- 8) Cushway, Cavaiola, 2021. *Affect of Culture, Morality and Competence toward Increasing the Performance*. . <http://www.publishingliterature.com>.
- 9) Dekker, Mascule, 2017. *Motivation and Application in Globalization Era*. <http://www.journalmotivation.com.id>. pp.155-165.
- 10) Dewi Indriasih, Aminul Fajri, Dinda F, 2022. Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasi, Sistem Pengendalian Internal, Kompetensi Pemerintah Desa, Transparansi, dan Aksesibilitas Laporan Keuangan Terhadap Akuntabilitas Pengelolaan Dana Desa. *Volum.03. No.04*.
- 11) Dimitrios Belias dan Athanasios Koustelios, 2019 *Progress of Organization and Performance: A Review*. *International Review of Management and Marketing* Vol. 4, No. 2, 2019, pp.132-149 ISSN: 2146-4405 www.econjournals.com
- 12) Dominique, Johnson, 2020. *Human Resource Management : Prestation Perspektif*. <http://humanresource.com>.
- 13) Donald, McEachern, Thomas, 2019. *Competence of Personal in Prospective Theories*. <http://www.journalhumanresource.com>.
- 14) Endang Setyanindyah, Umar Nimran, Kertahadi, Armanu Thoyib (2022) *The Effect of Human Resource Competence, Organizational Commitment and Transactional Leadership on Work Discipline, Performance and Service Quality*. *Journal of Management*. Vol. 2, No. 5, 2022.
- 15) Fatima Mohammed, 2022. *Performance: Service Quality and Organizational Commitment: A Correlation Study in Bahrain*. *International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology* Vol.3 No.5; May 2022
- 16) Follet, Marquett, 2018. *Human Resource Management and Performance in Quality and Quantity*. <http://humanresource.com>.
- 17) Furtwengler, Dale, 2018. *Performance of Human Resource Management*. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- 18) Gunistiyo, G., Budiyanto, B., & Suwitho, S. 2023. Developing Marketing Performance Through Order-Based Product Cloning Capability On Small Metal Industry. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, (11), 605-623.
- 19) Herry Martin, 2019. *The Rightness of Give Motivation and Service Quality in Performance toward the Progress of Organization*. <http://humanresource.com>.
- 20) Julie Yu-Chih Liu, Henry Houn-Gee Chen, James J. Jiang dan Gary Klein (2022) *Task Completion Competency and Project Management Performance: The Influence of Control and User Contribution*. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences*. Vol. 1(7), 59-67, July (2022) ISSN 2277-2502
- 21) Khalid Rehman, Zia Ur Rehman, Naveed Saif, Abdul Sattar Khan, Allah Nawaz dan Shafiq ur Rehman, 2022 *Impacts of Service Quality and Organizational Commitment: A Theoretical Model for Academicians in HEI of Developing Countries Like Pakistan*. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences* Vol. 3, No.1, January 2022, pp. 80–89 ISSN: 2225-8329 © 2022 HRMARS www.hrmars.com.
- 22) Mathis, Baron and Jackson, James N, 2018. *Strategic Human Resources-Frameworks for General Manager*. John Wiley and Sons, Inc, New York.
- 23) Nelson, Neil, 2017. *Human Resource Management In ServiceQuality Prospective*. Published McGraw Hill, New York.
- 24) Rothwell, H, 2017. *Planning For Good Competence Individual*, Libraries Unlimited, ISBN 0-313-32155-8.

- 25) Sunadji, Eka Afnan dkk, 2022. *The Role of Competence, Leadership, Motivation and Performance (Study on Public Enterprise of Water Resource Management of Ministry State-Owned Enterprise)*. International Journal of Business, Humanities and Technology Vol.3 No.5; May 2022.
- 26) Tri Wahyudi, 2021. Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada Bagian Layanan Pengadaan Barang dan Jasa, Sekretariat Daerah Kabupaten Lampung Tengah. Vol 02, No.02,.
- 27) Wilson, Bangun, 2018. *Management Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Revisi. Penerbit Rajawali Press, Jakarta.
- 28) Yusni, 2022. Pengaruh Kualitas layanan dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Pencegahan Fraud Pengadaan Barang/ dan Jasa Dengan Sistem Pengendalian Internal Pemerintah Sebagai Variabel Moderasi, Vol.05 No.02 jurnal Inobis,